

INNOVATIVE APPROACH TO DETECT BREAST CANCER BY VARIOUS TYPES OF MACHINE LEARNING ALGORITHM

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Abstract:- When the cells in the breast grow out of control, then the possibility of breast cancer arises. There are different types of breast cancer. The kind of breast cancer depends on which cells in the breast turn into cancer. Different parts of the breast can be affected by Breast Cancer. There are three main parts of the breast: lobules, ducts, and connective tissue. There are glands named lobules that produce milk. The ducts are tubes that carry milk to the nipple. The connective tissue (which consists of fibrous and fatty tissue) surrounds and holds everything together. Most breast cancers start in the ducts or lobules.

By Artificial Intelligence we can save many persons. By making a predictive model if we are able to understand if this is a malignant tumour or not. Then we can save many people's life.

Now we can save every woman from this dangerous disease. For this we have to detect breast cancer as early as possible. After detecting we should start the treatment for breast cancer.

Introduction:- Now-a-days breast cancer has now overtaken lung cancer as the most commonly diagnosed cancer in women worldwide, according to a research report released by the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) in December 2020. In the past two decades, the overall number of people diagnosed with cancer nearly doubled, from an estimated 10 million in 2000 to 19.3 million in 2020 [1]. As indicated by research, an established doctor can determine malignant tumor growth to have 79% precision while using the AI ML algorithm which gives an accuracy of 91%. In this work, AI strategies have been practical which incorporate Support Vector Machine (SVM), and Decision Tree Classifier (DT) and Random Forest Classifier (RF) [2]. We have discussed in abstract part the importance of detecting breast cancer. Now we have to discuss about the various Machine Learning algorithms. At first we have to load the dataset of breast cancer from scikit-learn datasets. Then we need to understand the parameters which is responsible for breast cancer. The parameters are:-

'worst fractal dimension', 'worst area', 'worst smoothness',

'mean smoothness', 'mean perimeter', 'perimeter error',
 'mean concave points', 'mean symmetry', 'mean fractal dimension',
 'radius error', 'texture error', 'concave points error', 'area error',
 'smoothness error', 'compactness error', 'concavity error',
 'mean concavity', 'symmetry error', 'worst radius',
 'fractal dimension error', 'worst texture',
 'worst perimeter', 'worst concavity', 'worst concave points',
 'worst symmetry', 'mean radius', 'mean texture',
 'mean compactness', 'mean area'.

We can see the feature names. Here we will detect if the tumour is benign or malignant and we will use the feature names or we can say the parameters.

Next we have to create a data frame from this target value and feature names. Now we will see the formed dataset

	mean radius	mean texture	mean perimeter	mean area	mean smoothness	mean compactness	mean concavity	mean concave points	mean symmetry	mean fractal dimension	...	texture	perimeter	area	si
0	17.99	10.38	122.80	1001.0	0.11840	0.27760	0.30010	0.14710	0.2419	0.07871	...	17.33	184.60	2019.0	
1	20.57	17.77	132.90	1326.0	0.08474	0.07864	0.08690	0.07017	0.1812	0.05667	...	23.41	158.80	1956.0	
2	19.69	21.25	130.00	1203.0	0.10960	0.15990	0.19740	0.12790	0.2069	0.05999	...	25.53	152.50	1709.0	
3	11.42	20.38	77.58	386.1	0.14250	0.28390	0.24140	0.10520	0.2597	0.09744	...	26.50	98.87	567.7	
4	20.29	14.34	135.10	1297.0	0.10030	0.13280	0.19800	0.10430	0.1809	0.05883	...	16.67	152.20	1575.0	
5	12.45	15.70	82.57	477.1	0.12780	0.17000	0.15780	0.08089	0.2087	0.07613	...	23.75	103.40	741.6	
6	18.25	19.98	119.60	1040.0	0.09463	0.10900	0.11270	0.07400	0.1794	0.05742	...	27.66	153.20	1606.0	
7	13.71	20.83	90.20	577.9	0.11890	0.16450	0.09366	0.05985	0.2196	0.07451	...	28.14	110.60	897.0	
8	13.00	21.82	87.50	519.8	0.12730	0.19320	0.18590	0.09353	0.2350	0.07389	...	30.73	106.20	739.3	
9	12.46	24.04	83.97	475.9	0.11860	0.23960	0.22730	0.08543	0.2030	0.08243	...	40.68	97.65	711.4	

Fig 1:-Loading the dataset

In this data frame the 1 indicates that the tumor is malignant and 0 represents that the tumor is benign.

Training And Testing The Data:- In this data frame the X denotes the the feature_names or the parameters and Y denotes the target values .Here we dividing the size into two parts.First one is the training part and second one is the testing part.At first we are training 910 data and testing 228 data.

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TRAIN TEST AND SPLIT
[12] from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
      X_train,X_test,Y_train,Y_test=train_test_split(X,Y,test_size=0.2,random_state=42)

[30] len(X_train)
      455

[31] len(X_test)
      114

[32] len(Y_train)
      455

len(Y_test)
      114

```

Fig2:-We are training 80% data and for this we are getting a good accuracy score.

Algorithms We Are Using In This Predictive System :-

Support Vector Machine:-Support Vector Machine or SVM is one of the most popular Supervised Learning algorithms, which is used for Classification as well as Regression problems. However, primarily, it is used for Classification problems in Machine Learning.The goal of the SVM algorithm is to create the best line or decision boundary that can segregate n-dimensional space into classes so that we can easily put the new data point in the correct category in the future. This best decision boundary is called a hyperplane.

SVM chooses the extreme points/vectors that help in creating the hyperplane. These extreme cases are called support vectors, and hence the algorithm is termed as Support Vector Machine.

Types Of Svm

SVM can be of two types:

Linear SVM: Linear SVM is used for linearly separable data, which means if a dataset can be classified into two classes by using a single straight line, then such data is termed as linearly separable data, and classifier is used called as Linear SVM classifier.

Non-linear SVM: Non-Linear SVM is used for non-linearly separated data, which means if a dataset cannot be classified by using a straight line, then such data is termed as non-linear data and classifier used is called as Non-linear SVM classifier.

Hyperplane And Support Vectors In The Svm Algorithm:

Hyperplane: There can be multiple lines/decision boundaries to segregate the classes in n-dimensional space, but we need to find out the best decision boundary that helps to classify the data points. This best boundary is known as the hyperplane of SVM. The dimensions of the hyperplane depend on the features present in the dataset, which means if there are 2 features, then the hyperplane will be a straight line. And if there are 3 features, then the hyperplane will be a 2-dimension plane. We always create a hyperplane that has a maximum margin, which means the maximum distance between the data points.

Support Vectors:

The data point or the vector which are closest to the hyperplane and for which the position of the hyperplane gets affected. Those data points are called support vectors.

The Accuracy score of Support Vector Machine Algorithm:-


```

SUPPORT VECTOR MACHINE NOW IMPLEMENTING

In [ ]: from sklearn.svm import SVC

classification_rbf=SVC(kernel='rbf')
classification_rbf.fit(X_train,Y_train)

/usr/local/lib/python3.9/dist-packages/sklearn/utils/validation.py:1143: DataConversionWarning: A column-vector y was passed when a 1d array was expected. Please change the shape of y to (
y = column or 1d(y, warn=True)

In [ ]: SVC
SVC()

In [ ]: Y_pred=classification_rbf.predict(X_test)

In [ ]: from sklearn.metrics import confusion_matrix
cfm=confusion_matrix(Y_test,Y_pred)
cfm
array([[37,  6],
       [ 0, 71]])

In [ ]: classification_rbf.score(X_test,Y_test)
0.9473684210526315

```

Fig3:-The accuracy score of SVM Algorithm

Decision Tree Classification Algorithm:-

There is a very important algorithm in supervised learning named Decision Tree Classifier Algorithm. This algorithm is mostly preferred for solving classification problems. It is a tree-structured classifier where the internal nodes represent the dataset and the branches represent the decision rules and each leaf node represents the outcome.

In a Decision tree, there are two nodes, which are the Decision Node and Leaf Node. Decision nodes are used to make any decision and have multiple branches, whereas Leaf nodes are the output of those decisions and do not contain any further branches.

Decision Tree Terminologies:-

Root Node: Root node is the starting point of the decision tree classifier algorithm, it represents the full dataset.

Leaf Node: Leaf nodes are used to represent the final output.

Splitting: We divide the decision node/root node into sub-nodes according to the given conditions by splitting method.

Branch/Subtree: By Splitting method we get a branch or subtree.

Pruning: By Pruning we process unwanted branches from the tree.

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DECISION TREE IMPLEMENTATION
from sklearn.tree import DecisionTreeClassifier
dtc=DecisionTreeClassifier(criterion='gini')
dtc.fit(X_train,Y_train)
DecisionTreeClassifier()
Y_Pred=dtc.predict(X_test)

ACCURACY SCORE OF DECISION TREE
dtc.score(X_test,Y_test)
0.9473684210526315

```

Accuracy Score Of The Model With Decision Tree Algorithm:-

Fig4:-Accuracy score of Decision Tree algorithm

Random Forest Classifier :-

Random Forest is one of the most important Machine Learning algorithm. It is a algorithm of supervised learning technique. It is used for both classification technique and regression problems. Random Forest Classifier is based on ensemble learning. It is a process of combining multiple classifiers to solve a complex problem and to improve the performance of the model.

As the name suggests, "Random Forest is a classifier which contains a number of decision trees on various subsets of the given dataset and takes the average to improve the predictive accuracy of that dataset." Instead of relying on one decision tree, the random forest takes the prediction from each tree and based on the majority votes of predictions, and it predicts the final output.

We will get higher accuracy and we can prevent the problem of overfitting by this type of algorithm with the greater number of trees.

Accuracy Score Of The Model With This Algorithm:-

```

THE RANDOM FOREST CLASSIFIER IMPLEMENTING
from sklearn.ensemble import RandomForestClassifier
rfc=RandomForestClassifier(n_estimators=100,criterion='gini')
rfc.fit(X_train,Y_train)
<ipython-input-26-677a6ae3e332>:3: DataConversionWarning: A column-vector y was passed when a 1d array was expected. Please change the shape of y to (n_samples,), for example using ravel().
rfc.fit(X_train,Y_train)
RandomForestClassifier()
RandomForestClassifier()
Y_Predict=rfc.predict(X_test)

ACCURACY SCORE OF THE RANDOM FOREST TREES
rfc.score(X_test,Y_test)
0.9649122807017544

```

Fig5:-Accuracy score of Random Forest Classifier algorithm

Conclusion:-

Why should we talk about Breast Cancer? Because it is the second leading cause of death among women in the world. We should know the general signs & symptoms of breast cancers. Also we should know the parameters by which we can determine if this is a malignant tumour or not. Breast Cancer snatches millions of women and men's life from the world. That's why we need to spread awareness. 1 in 8 women and 1 in 1000 men gets affected by Breast Cancer. For making a good predictive model we should take a very good dataset. We need to take care of every data which are responsible for breast cancer. We need to train a good amount of data to the machine for getting a good accuracy score

There are over 3.8 million breast cancer survivors in the US. That's why we need to spread awareness to save people and we should use the blessing of Artificial Intelligence.

Future Scope Of This Type Of Predictive Model:-

I have done my prediction model with data but we can do the same predictive model using MRI (Magnetic Resonance Imaging) reports using CNN, and if we can detect the breast cancer with a good accuracy score then as early as possible we can start the treatment of the patient so that we can save the life of the patient. Now-a-days when Artificial Intelligence is helping us in our daily life then this type of predictive models can be created and we also can inject this machine learning algorithm logic into a website or into an application. Then easily we can detect the breast cancer and that's how we can save millions of people's life.

References:-

- [1]. 'WHO | Breast cancer', WHO.
<http://www.who.int/cancer/prevention/diagnosis-screening/breast-cancer/en/> (accessed Feb. 18, 2020)

[2].Breast Cancer Detection Using Machine Learning Algorithms Kumar
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